

Master thesis on Sound and Music Computing
Universitat Pompeu Fabra

Event Recognition of Domestic Sounds using Semi-Supervised Learning

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Dedication

To my true friends.

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Abstract

The goals of this project are the creation of a new dataset of sounds that belong to the domestic environment, called DomesticFSD2018, and to research on methods for the automatic classification of them. A Semi-Supervised approach is used to evaluate the possibility of exploiting samples that are not manually-verified. The purpose of this is to avoid the need of experts and save as many resources as possible in the validation process, that usually takes a lot of time and energies. The train set of DomesticFSD2018 is composed of a trustable (manually-verified) portion of data and a non-trustable (which has received no human validation and can be potentially inaccurate or mislabeled) one. A purely supervised learning approach is firstly followed, training models with only the trustable portion, and both trustable and non-trustable portions of data. Then the semi-supervised learning approach is experimented, using the models trained in the previous step to make predictions on non-trustable data. The samples predicted with the highest level of confidence are added to the train set, and finally, the classifier is re-trained using the updated and larger train set. In both cases, the technologies used are Support Vector Machines using MFCCs' properties as input. The semi-supervised approach shows better results and allows us to add a considerable amount of non-trustable data to the trustable portion of the dataset.

Keywords: Semi-supervised learning; Domestic Environment; Machine Learning; Freesound Datasets Platform.

Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Conceptual background and motivation

Sounds play a critical role in our life, especially when it comes to an understanding of the environment around us. Even if we don't think about it, in every moment we are processing lots of information that is in the shape of sound waves, that is consequently processed by our auditory system and sent as electrical impulses to our brain. This can be the case with natural sounds, which can trigger some basic human behaviors, like the feeling of danger, or artificial sounds, for example, an alarm, for communication purposes.

Said this, Audio Event Recognition is the discipline that aims, ideally, to classify automatically certain specific events, considering as source audio fragments of real-life recordings. The term "audio event", or "sound event", refers to a specific sound produced by a distinct physical sound source[1]. A lot of work has already been done in speech recognition and music, but anything relevant has done on "generic" sounds. The reasons are multiple, and we will go through them, but, in general, we can say that the problem was less critical and obvious than music and speech recognition. Compared to speech, which has a relatively small, closed set of different categories (phonemes) and rules for how they can follow each other (language model) or music that follows specific rules (notes in particular frequency

ratios forming chords, key and pitch evolution during a musical piece), the categories and sequences of environmental sounds are not so straightforward to define. Sounds can be organized into categories based on different properties, such as the sound source (e.g., cup), its production mechanism (e.g., hit), or even the source properties (e.g., metal), and the same sound can belong to many different categories, depending on the chosen property (sound when hitting a metallic cup). Also, there are no specific rules on how environmental sounds co-occur. For this reason, building a database for environmental sounds is a complicated task, with the choice of classes usually dictated by the targeted research, and the size limited by practical aspects of data collection[1].

Comparable problems such as object detection in images are showing astonishing results[2, 3]. One of the most important reasons for this success is ImageNet, a large-scale, openly available dataset that provides more than 1 million images labeled with 1000 object categories with a solid ground truth. One of the current goals in audio research is to create automatic audio event recognition systems that are, hopefully, comparable to the state-of-the-art in recognizing objects in real-world images[4]. Acoustic monitoring would allow the recognition of physical events such as glass breaking (from somebody breaking into a house), a gunshot, or a car crash. In comparison to video monitoring, acoustic monitoring can be advantageous in many scenarios, since sounds travel through obstacles, is not affected by lighting conditions, and capturing sound typically consumes less power. Methods that automatically produce descriptions of multimedia items could lead to new, more accurate search methods that are based on the content of the materials. It can also be utilized in many application areas related to the human interaction with the environment, like lifelogging[5] and health activity monitoring[6].

Existing datasets for sound recognition are scarce and most of them small [7], but a lot of research and work is being done in the last years. For example, Google with the development of the Audio Set project[4], or the Music Technology Group in Barcelona with the development of the Freesound Datasets Platform[8].

The second issue, instead, consists of how to use artificial intelligence in the best

way to achieve this goal. Nowadays Machine Learning and Deep Learning algorithms are used in every field, also in speech and music recognition, but they've been not enough explored on generic sounds.

This work focuses on the subset of sounds that occur in domestic environments. The ontology followed is the Audio Set one, that is also the one used in the Freesound Datasets Platform. The ontology is a hierarchical ontology with a semantical-based tree structure, where each node represents a category that can have, eventually, a different number of children.

For this project I've chosen to work on sounds that belong to the domestic environment, so all the sounds that you can listen both actively and passively while you are, for example, sitting on your sofa, like a door squeaking or the ring of the microwave that indicates that the food is ready. One of the reasons behind this choice is the rapid increase in the development and research of technologies regarding smart homes in the last years. Some big companies, like Google with *Google Home* and Amazon with *Amazon Echo*, are releasing products with the goal of monitoring events in the domestic environment. Contributions from this project could be useful in these kinds of applications.

The first step is, as mentioned before, to build a consistent dataset, and I will do it starting from the Freesound Datasets Platform.

To be able to achieve an automatic recognition of sounds, proper models need to be trained, trying to obtain the best result possible. To do this, data that have the role to be the "model" to follow is needed so that the models can be trained in the best way possible. However, nowadays the situation is very far from this. Two big datasets will be analyzed: AudioSet by Google and Freesound Datasets by MTG. The first one will be investigated because is where the ontology used in this project comes from, and the second one because is where the sounds are taken from, exploiting its architecture.

The first problem is that having "free" sounds available is not easy. It usually happens that sounds that are online, organized in some way (sample packs, etc.),

are proprietary, and so not openly available. The second one is the need to verify the nature and the characteristics of the audio samples that are recorded or collected. This procedure needs the involvement of a lot of people and time. Furthermore, to have a trustworthy annotation, you need to have more than one annotator validating a single sample. Regarding this, the Freesound Datasets Platform relies on the Freesound contents. Freesound is an online collaborative sound database where people with diverse interests share recorded sound samples under Creative Commons licenses[9]. Being the sounds under these licenses, they allow the people to work on them without paying. The verification from annotators is still needed, but being already samples uploaded and labeled on Freesound by the community, the work should be faster and more focused.

Another major problem is the creation of an exhaustive ontology. When you classify something, you need to define classes, and in this case, we would like to identify all the classes that represent the "entire world". But also here, Gemmeke states: "applying these rules over web-scale text yields a massive set of terms, which are then sorted regarding how well they represent sounds - calculated as a combination of overall frequency of occurrence with how exclusively they are identified as hyponyms of "sound" rather than other terms"[4]. The use of this mechanism means that also the ontology was created automatically with some statistical algorithm, and this lets me think of some possible lack of consistency.

The subset of the ontology under the category named "Domestic sounds, home sounds" will be extracted from the Freesound Datasets Platform, together with the audio samples related to it. To make the classification easier only one level of the hierarchy is considered. The methodology for the experiments is inspired by the one illustrated in this paper[10], where models trained on the trustable portion of our dataset can be exploited to make classification predictions on the non-trustable one. The samples predicted with the highest level of confidence, depending on a chosen threshold, are then machine-labeled and used to increase the train set. This mechanism allows us to select from the non-trustable portion of the dataset, the one that can potentially contain inaccurate or mislabeled samples, the ones that, having

a level of confidence equal or higher of a selected threshold, can be considered as trustable.

1.2 Thesis outline

In Chapter 2, the previous work done in this direction is shown. First, the characteristics of a well-built dataset and the challenges involved during the building phase are covered. Also, some examples of already existing datasets related to ours are investigated. After that, the technologies that have been required in the classification of events will be presented, together with all the processes that need to be done from the raw audio to the feature vector that is used to feed the models. Lastly, the meaning of semi-supervised learning and the reason why this approach is important for our project are explained.

In Chapter 3 the methodology used for this project is presented, from the dataset building choices to the choices of the different models and experiments.

In Chapter 4 the results are shown in the form of tables and confusion matrices, every of which is commented and explained.

In Chapter 5 the conclusions are drawn, and some ideas for future work are suggested.

In Chapter 6 information on the reproducibility of the experiments are presented.

Chapter 2

State of the Art

2.1 Computational auditory scene analysis

Computational auditory scene analysis (CASA) is the study of auditory scene analysis by computational means. In essence, CASA systems are "machine listening" systems that aim to separate mixtures of sound sources in the same way that human listeners do. CASA includes a wide set of algorithms and "machine listening" systems that deal with the analysis of acoustic scenes. Most of them model to some extent the human auditory system and its mechanisms and aim to detect, identify, separate and segregate sounds in the same way that humans do[11]. In the last years, an increasing number of researchers have approached this field. However, a set of tasks, each with a well-defined evaluation framework and commonly used datasets do not yet exist.

The type of information to be extracted from sound depends on the application. However, the typical sound analysis tasks can be characterized into a few high-level categories. In *classification*, the goal is to categorize an audio recording into one of a set of predefined categories. For example, a sound scene classification system might classify audio as one of a set of categories including home, street, and office. In *event detection*, the goal is to locate in time the occurrences of a specific type of sound or sounds, either by finding each instance when the sounds happen or by

finding all the temporal positions when the sounds are active. There are also other more specific tasks, such as the one of our interest, called *audio tagging*, which aims to assign automatically one, or a set, of tags to a single, usually short, clip (Figure 1). [1]

Figure 1: Tasks CASA from [1]

2.1.1 Technical Challenges

The core tasks of detection and classification require using several techniques related to audio signal processing and machine learning. For example, typical computational analysis systems first extract some acoustic features from the input signal, and Supervised classifiers such as neural networks can be used for classification and detection[12].

A sound, or audio, event is a fragment of a real recording. It's a sound that we perceive as a separate, individual entity that we can name and recognize, and, conversely, whose acoustic characteristics we can recall based on its description. Sound events are the building blocks of a sound scene and facilitate its interpretation[1]. In contrast, an audio scene is usually composed by a series of audio events, that are usually divided in characteristic sounds depending on the environment, and others that are more "unpredictable". These can be humans, animals or objects, and the sounds are usually representative of the interaction between them (the use of one of them, the collision, the break,etc).

Compared to other types of audio, sound events that belong to the same category, generally, have a very high *acoustic variability*. For example, the words in speech exhibit acoustic variability due to aspects like intonation, accent, speaker identity,

and mood, but they always have the same underlying structure of phonemes that is employed when building acoustic models. This property of speech makes its automatic recognition "easier" compared to the recognition of "sounds of things" in general. However, some sound categories do exhibit structure, for example, footsteps that are composed of individual sounds of a foot tapping the ground, therefore having a temporal structure which can differ due to walking speed, surface, etc. Other sound categories are vast, and a structure is noticeable only in the subcategories, for example, birdsong being similar just for the same species, possibly requiring a different and more detailed labeling scheme. This introduces a level of difficulty in the tasks mentioned above because using a feature based system, facing some overlap in the acoustic nature of these sounds we automatically have more possibilities of making a wrong classification of them.

2.1.2 Audio Classification and Tagging

In the classification task, a segment of audio is classified into a single and predefined class for single-label classification, or into multiple predefined classes for multi-label classification, depending on the target application. Audio analysis systems performing multi-label classification are also referred to as audio tagging systems [1].

Single-Label Classification

For single-label classification, the learning examples are audio segments with a single class annotated throughout. The annotations are encoded into target outputs which are used in the learning stage together with audio signals. In this case, classes are mutually exclusive. On FSD Platform the dataset that we are extracting is characterized by single-labeled samples, where the label is referred to the source of the sound. The sound happening in the clip is not described by its start and end time, so the labeling is said to be *weak*. In contrast, when the sound start and end time are specified along with its category name, the labeling is called *strong*.

Multi-Label Classification (Tagging)

For multi-label classification or audio tagging, the learning examples contain audio annotated similarly as for single-label classification, only this time multiple classes can be active at the same time in the annotations.

Many of the challenges mentioned above are related to the acoustics of sound scenes and events. First, the acoustic characteristics of even a single class of sounds can be highly diverse. For example in the case of class "Door", the acoustics can vary enormously depending on the size of the door and the way it is open or closed. Second, in realistic environments, there can be many different types of sounds, some of whose acoustic characteristics may be very close to the target sounds [1]. For example, the acoustics of a working vacuum cleaner can be close to the sound of a hairdryer or a blender. We will see many of these cases in the domestic environment. Thirdly, an audio signal captured by a microphone is affected by the channel coupling (impulse response) between the source and microphone, which may alter the signal sufficiently to prevent matching of models developed to recognize the sound. Finally, in realistic environments, there are almost always multiple sources producing sound simultaneously.

In addition to these complications related to the acoustics of sound scenes and events, there are also several fundamental challenges associated with the development of computational methods. For example, if we are aiming at the development of techniques able to classify and detect a large number of sounds, there is the need for a taxonomy that defines the classes to be used. Audio Set is the first attempt of ontology that should be the representation in categories of all the sounds that a human can find around him, but we will see that being the task very difficult, it's not perfect yet.

The computational methods used are heavily based on machine learning, where the parameters of a system are automatically obtained by using examples of the target (and non-target) sounds [1]. In contrast to the situation in image classification, currently available datasets that can be used to develop computational scene and

event scene analysis systems are more limited in size, diversity, and number of event instances, even though recent contributions such as AudioSet[4] and Freesound Datasets[8] have significantly reduced this gap.

2.2 Dataset

The data includes both audio material and reference metadata associated with it (e.g., class labels). Data acquisition is an important stage of the development, as the performance of the developed system is highly dependent on the data used to develop it.[1]

The number of classes or the types of sounds that can be classified is constrained by the availability of data that is used to train classifiers, and by the accuracy of the systems. The accuracy that can be achieved is affected by many factors, such as the similarity of classes to be distinguished from each other, the diversity of each class, external factors such as interfering noises, the quality and amount of training data, and the actual computational methods used [1].

Essentially, the aim is to collect as realistic as possible acoustic signals in conditions which are as close as possible to the intended target application. Metadata should include a ground truth information which is often manually annotated during the data collection. On FSD the sounds are taken from Freesound, where they are uploaded on a web platform together with the tags associated to them by the community. Collected data should have sufficient amount of representative examples of all sound classes necessary for the target application to enable the acoustic models to generalize well.

The audio must represent the modeled phenomena such that the models learned from it will represent the variability in the acoustic properties expected in the application. The presence of all categories relevant to a sound event detection task will provide the required coverage, making a dataset suitable for the given task. These are the main properties that a well-built dataset should have:

- Coverage: The dataset should contain as many different categories as are relevant to the task (perhaps including future evolutions).
- Variability: For each category, there should be examples with variable conditions of generation, recording, etc.
- Size: For each category, there should be sufficiently many examples. Otherwise, the training of a system results in a weak model.

Variability for a dataset of sound events can be achieved by having multiple audio instances from the same sound source, recorded in different acoustic conditions (similar to examples of speech from the same person in different situations), and also cases from multiple sound sources that belong to the same category (similar to collecting speech from various persons). Variability of natural sound sources is much higher than of non-natural sources (the same dog will bark in many different ways, but a given fire alarm will always make the same sound); therefore, for some sound categories, it may be unnecessary to have many examples with the same acoustic content. Due to the high acoustic variability of sound events, it is impossible to obtain examples of all categories in all conditions; therefore, the acceptable size and variability for a training dataset depend strongly on the expected variability of the application as represented by the test data.

The choice of target application typically dictates the need for specific categories of sounds, which in turn defines the data collection process concerning content and diversity. The labels attached to the training data define the categories to be learned; on the test data, the labels dictate the desired output against which to evaluate recognition performance.

The following properties should characterize the labels:

- Representation: A label should be a good descriptor of the sound scene or event, of sufficient descriptive power to allow understanding of the sound properties based on the label.

- Non-ambiguity: A label should be unequivocal and have a clear one-to-one correspondence to the type of sound to which it applies.

Sound event labels usually consist of a very short and concise description of the sound as perceived by humans. The interpretation of the sound regarding its source is related to so-called everyday listening. According to Gaver[13], sounds are caused by the interaction of materials and convey information about those materials and their interactions; at the most basic level sounds can be categorized as involving solids, liquids, or gases, with a few basic-level events (e.g., impacts, pouring, explosions).

Similar to the case of sound scene labels, a sound event label may be attached to an entire recording, indicating the presence of the described sound in the audio without specifying the actual temporal location of the sound event. In this case, the label is referred to as a weak label or a tag. A single audio example may have multiple associated tags[7]. In its most informative form, a sound event label has associated temporal boundaries to mark the sound event's onset and offset, making it a *strong* label. In this case, an event label characterizes a certain segment of the audio recording which represents a sound event instance, with multiple instances of the same category being possible in the same recording.

2.3 Technologies

2.3.1 Audio Processing

Audio is prepared and processed for machine learning algorithms in the audio processing phase of the overall system design. This phase consists of two stages: pre-processing, in which the audio signal is processed to reduce the effect of noise or to emphasize the target sounds, and acoustic feature extraction, in which the audio signal is transformed into a compact representation. [1]

Pre-processing

Pre-processing is applied to the audio signal before acoustic feature extraction if needed. The main role of this stage is to enhance certain characteristics of the incoming signal in order to maximize audio analysis performance in the later phases of the analysis system. This is achieved by reducing the effects of noise or by emphasizing the target sounds in the signal.

Feature Extraction

The audio analysis is commonly based on acoustic features extracted from the audio signal to represent it in a compact and non-redundant way. For recognition algorithms, the necessary property of the acoustic features is low variability among features extracted from examples assigned to the same class, and at the same time high variability allowing distinction between features extracted from example assigned to different classes.

The role of feature extraction is to transform the signal into a representation which maximizes the sound recognition performance of the analysis system. The acoustic features provide a numerical representation of the signal content relevant for machine learning, characterizing the signal with values which have a connection to its physical properties, for example, signal energy, its distribution in frequency, and change over time. The processing pipeline in feature extraction is similar for many types of acoustic features used in analysis and consists of frame blocking, windowing, spectrum calculation, and subsequent analysis (Figure 2).

The most common transformation used for audio signals is the discrete Fourier transform (DFT), which represents the signal with a superposition of sinusoidal base functions, each base being characterized by a magnitude and phase. Examples of other transformation methods used for audio signals are constant-Q transform (CQT) and discrete wavelet transform (DWT).

The most common acoustic features used to represent spectral content of audio signals are Mel-band energies and Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCCs).

Figure 2: Feature extraction pipeline. Image from [1]

Their design is based on the observation that human auditory perception focuses only on magnitudes of frequency components. The perception of these magnitudes is highly non-linear, and, in addition, the perception of frequencies is also non-linear. Following perception, these acoustic feature extraction techniques use a non-linear representation for magnitudes (power spectra and logarithm) and a non-linear frequency scaling (Mel-frequency scaling). The non-linear frequency scaling is implemented using filter banks which integrate the spectrum at non-linearly spaced frequency ranges, with narrow band-pass filters at low frequencies and with larger bandwidth at higher frequencies. Mel-band energies and MFCCs provide a compact and smooth representation of the local spectrum, but neglect temporal changes in the spectrum over time.

The feature design and parameters used in the extraction commonly rely on prior knowledge and assumptions about the content of the acoustic signal, which in some analysis tasks can lead to sub-optimal performance. For example, selected length of the analysis frame or number of mMel-bands might be optimal only for a subset of

sound classes involved in the analysis. Unsupervised feature learning can be used to learn better-fitted feature representations for specific tasks. The feature learning can also be incorporated into the overall learning process through end-to-end learning, thus avoiding explicit learning of the feature representation. In this approach, the correspondence of the input signal (usually raw audio signal or spectrogram) and desired recognition output is learnt directly.

2.3.2 Support Vector Machine

In machine learning, support vector machines (SVMs, also support vector networks [14]) are supervised learning models with associated learning algorithms that analyze data used for classification and regression analysis. Given a set of training examples, each marked as belonging to one or the other of two categories, an SVM training algorithm builds a model that assigns new examples to one category or the other, making it a non-probabilistic binary linear classifier (although methods such as Platt scaling exist to use SVM in a probabilistic classification setting). An SVM model is a representation of the examples as points in space, mapped so that the examples of the separate categories are divided by a clear gap that is as wide as possible. New examples are then mapped into that same space and predicted to belong to a category based on which side of the gap they fall.

In addition to performing linear classification, SVMs can efficiently perform a non-linear classification using what is called the kernel trick, implicitly mapping their inputs into high-dimensional feature spaces.

In audio classification, Support Vector Machines have been widely used before the "Deep learning renaissance" that we are experiencing today [15, 16]. They have been usually used with features that are representative of the sound as input. In this project, we will use this technology to test our experiments because they are more flexible and less time consuming for the semi-supervised learning implementation. This is because we are not searching for the best accuracy in, but we want to make considerations on different dataset splits.

2.3.3 Semi-Supervised Learning

Nowadays, while many of the existing audio datasets are small, a large amount of audio content is available in sharing sites like Freesound. This leads to a typical scenario where a small portion of reliable annotations are available from manually-labeled datasets, along with a large amount of noisy, potentially unreliable web audio data. The goal of Semi-Supervised learning techniques is to exploit the availability of unlabeled data for model training and improvement. This approach is very attractive and useful to enhance the robustness of existing classifiers, because it does not require the intervention of human annotators [17, 18]. Two broad categories of SSL have been investigated to date: self-training [19] and co-training [20, 21]. Self-training is a technique that permits to automatically annotate unlabeled data by using a preexisting model trained on a smaller set of labeled data, and that's the one that we will use. Usually, those instances of the unlabeled data set that are predicted with the highest degree of confidences are added to the training set (together with the respective labels), and the classifier is re-trained with the new (larger) set. This procedure is then repeated iteratively until a certain target performance is achieved (or until no more unlabeled candidate data is available), in our case just one time. In this way, self-training allows to automatically annotate unlabeled (or wrongly labeled) data through consecutive iterations. However, it can suffer from a number of issues, especially error propagation, apart from the longer training times due to the iterations required. The effectiveness of self-training has been demonstrated in various areas, including spoken language understanding [22], handwritten digit and text classification [23], and sound event classification [24]. Self-training is the technique that will be explored in our experiments.

Chapter 3

Methods

3.1 Dataset

One of the essential parts of this project was the creation of the dataset. As we have already mentioned, there is a lack of consistent datasets for the domestic event recognition task, and the creation of it has been one of the biggest challenges of the project. In this Section, we present DomesticFSD2018, a dataset of 13 categories that belong to the domestic environment that was built for this project, as well as the comparison between the already existing datasets in the field. The dataset structure was built with the Freesound Datasets Platform [8], a platform run by the Music Technology Group in Barcelona that starts with a mapping of Freesound [9] samples in the Audio Set [4] ontology, based on metadata, and continues providing annotation mechanisms in order to validate the membership of each sample to the assigned category. The choice of relying on this platform was made for essentially four reasons:

- annotation mechanism already implemented in the platform and community-based for providing non-biased annotations
- potentially very large number of samples
- audio samples under open licenses (Creative Commons)

- labels at clip level referred to the entirety of the sample

<i>Dataset (release year)</i>	<i>#clips</i>	<i>clip length</i>	<i>dataset duration</i>	<i>#classes</i>	<i>do authors provide audio? / license type</i>
GTZAN (2002)	1000	30s	8.33h	10 – balanced	yes / questionable © permission
Ballroom (2006)	698	≈30s	≈5.81h	8 – unbalanced	yes / questionable © permission
Million Song Dataset (2011)	1M	-	-	<i>external resources</i>	no
MagnaTagATune (2009)	25,856	≈30s	215.46h	188 – unbalanced	yes / open license
AudioSet (2017)	≈2.1M	10s	≈5833h	527 – (un)balanced*	no
TUT Acoustic Scenes (2016)	1560	30s	13h	15 – balanced	yes / open license
UrbanSound8k (2014)	8732	≤4s	8.75h	10 – balanced	yes / open license
ESC-50 (2015)	2000	5s	2.78h	50 – balanced	yes / open license
FSD early snapshot (2017)	23,519	≤90s	119h	398 – unbalanced	yes / open license

Figure 3: Relevant datasets in audio recognition from [8]

Furthermore, we can see from Figure 4 that the early snapshot of FSD has a very big potential compared to the majority of previous datasets considering the number of clips, the number of categories and the availability of audio samples with open licenses. We can see, in particular, that Audio Set, that is the most interesting one for our task, does not provide audio (Figure 4) and, according to [8], even though the dataset annotations have been manually validated, around 15% of the categories present a quality estimate with a score below 50%.

The dataset has in total is made by two main parts:

- trustable data (1606 entries)
- non-trustable data (6912 entries)

Trustable data, or High-Quality data, is the part of the dataset that was manually verified by human annotators. They are those samples that we know for sure that they belong to their category. It's the ground truth that we will rely on. Non-trustable data is a piece of data composed of somewhat unreliable annotation. The characteristics of this portion of the dataset will be described in detail in Chapter 3.1.5.

As previously mentioned, the subset of the ontology under the category named "Domestic sounds, home sounds" is extracted from the Freesound Datasets Platform, together with the audio samples related to it. Only one level of the hierarchy is considered to make the classification easier. This choice forced us to collapse the children of two categories in DomesticFSD2018 in their parents, increasing the variability of these categories. These are:

- Door
 - Slam
 - Sliding door
 - Squeak
 - Knock
 - Tap
 - Doorbell

- Typing
 - Computer Keyboard
 - Typewriter

Although the sound of a "Computer Keyboard" and a "Typewriter" can be different in the typing mechanism but not too much in the temporal patterns and tonality, the children of "Door" are acoustically and semantically different, adding a lot of semantic variability in the category. This variability, as we will see later, will penalize us in the classification of "Door" samples. By the way, it's the only category with this not-so-clean structure. In another experiment this factor could be handled differently, probably doing experiments preserving the hierarchy and using multi-label annotations (ex. a sample tagged as both "Door" and "Slam").

Furthermore, being the need of data more and more growing due to the increase in the complexity of models, like neural networks, we will use some techniques, called semi-supervised methods, that try to exploit some non-trustable data as they were

trustable. These approaches are currently very utilized because manually verified data needs annotators.

3.1.1 Building

The dataset is released as `train.csv`, `test.csv`, and `non-trustable.csv`. These files refer to audio samples that are in the folders called `audio_train`, `audio_test`, and `audio_non-trustable`. Each instance is represented by filename, category and annotation(`manually annotated(trustable)=1` vs `non-manually annotated(untrustable)=0`). The filename of each sample is its corresponding Freesound id, in order to make the reference in Freesound easier if needed. All the files are in `.wav` format and 44100 Hz as sampling rate. The split of the train and test set is done with a ratio of 60/40 (scikit-learn[25] function `model_selection.train_test_split` used for this). This ratio allows the test set to be bigger compared to common techniques (80/20, 70/30), but the choice was made in order to have wider test set that maintains its validity (and it's not too small) also when we will increase the training set size with portions of non-trustable data (Table 1).

- train set = 974 samples
- test set = 632 samples

Annotation Process

The annotation process consists in verifying the audio clips that later will be included, or not, in our dataset. The sounds presented are already associated with some classes in the AudioSet ontology, based on:

- the original tags provided by Freesound users
- a mapping from those tags to the AudioSet classes

In the first case, the tags are chosen freely and can be potentially wrong or inaccurate. In the second one, the mapping is not perfect and can be incomplete or

Category	n samples train	n samples test	Acronym
Coin (dropping)	73	54	coi
Cupboard open or close	54	32	cup
Door	89	58	dor
Drawer open or close	74	42	dra
Keys jangling	72	49	key
Microwave oven	61	36	mic
Packing tape, duct tape	53	42	pac
Scissors	75	51	sci
Toilet flush	92	64	toi
Typing	98	55	typ
Vacuum cleaner	61	41	vac
Writing	100	47	wrt
Zipper (clothing)	72	60	zip

Table 1: Trustable set

generate mislabeled samples. For these reasons the samples need to be verified. In this project manually verified data will be used to make considerations on the unreliable portion. The latter, as we will see in Chapter 3.1.5, is the result of the aforementioned conditions and with some considerations can be used to our advantage.

The annotation system of the Freesound Dataset Platform was exploited for this task. The user was presented of 60 samples, five pages of 12 samples each, all of the same category. The following response types were presented, and only one-per-sample could be chosen:

- *PP* = Present and Predominant. The type of sound described is clearly present and predominant. This means there are no other types of sound, except for low/mild background noise.
- *PNP* = Present but NOT Predominant. The type of sound described is present, but the audio clip also contains other salient types of sound and/or strong background noise.
- *NP* = Not Present. The type of sound described is not present in the audio clip

- U = Unsure. Not sure whether the type of sound described is present or not

Figure 4: Response types

These are the votes that can be assigned in the annotation phase. Only one vote-per-sample can be assigned, and one user can annotate each sample only one time. The ground truth is verified when a sample has two votes of the same kind (*inter-annotator agreement*). When this condition is verified, the annotation phase is closed for that sample in that category. This, however, does not mean that if the sample falls in two categories of the dataset during the mapping, the ground truth for it could not be generated in another category. This is when the multi-labelness property of the samples is shown. (ex. a sample is made by two samples and falls into two categories due to the metadata assigned on Freesound). Later we will analyze how this concept has shown in our dataset. After the voting process, each sample is represented by a *distribution of response types*. Considerations on these distributions allow us to understand the reliability of each sample, assigning it to the correct *group of vote distributions* related to its category. First, there is the search of the ground truth. During the annotation process, a sample is presented to annotators until it gets two equal votes by two different people. When that happens, it means that we have a ground truth for that samples and we don't need further annotations. When the ground truth is not verified, we have to make some considerations and write some rules in order to send the remaining samples to the most suitable group of vote distributions. In our case we followed these rules from *distributions of response types* to category-wise *groups of vote distributions*:

- $PP_group = \text{ground truth}(PP*2) + PP(\text{only one})$
- $PNP_group = \text{ground truth}(PNP*2) + (PP+PNP) + (PP+PNP+U)$
- $NP_group = NP + *$
- $U_group = PNP(\text{only one}) + \text{ground truth}(U*2) + (PP+U) + (PNP+U)$

Once the groups of vote distributions are obtained, we differentiate the trustable portion of the dataset from the non-trustable one in this way:

- $trustable = PP_group$
- $non-trustable = PNP_group + U_group + \text{candidates}(\text{samples with no response types/unvoted})$

The non-trustable portion of the dataset will be described in detail in Chapter 3.1.5.

FAQ addition & Metadata support

During the annotation process, some classes present certain ambiguities (explained in Chapter 3.1.3), and people have doubts while annotating. This can lead inconsistent annotations, as well as time wasted in search of agreement. Frequently Asked Question is a way to overcome these issues. FAQs were created, or checked if already existing, for the categories of "Domestic sounds, home sounds" with the help of my supervisor.

Showing the metadata coming from Freesound could help the annotator identifying the source even if, acoustically speaking, the source is not clear (Figure 5). In this way, we can hope that the machine learns to recognize sounds that are not easy-recognizable by humans. By the way, some annotations were done previously, and we can see in the multi-label analysis that some sounds are being labeled with two different categories as ground truth (ex. cupboard, drawer, door). One thing to make clear is that the metadata should help the decision but not define it. The

final decision is always made by human annotators and doesn't rely automatically on metadata.

Figure 5: FAQs shown during the annotation of "Bathtub (filling or washing)"

Examples, verification and false verification examples

In order to give a sort of quality estimation to the annotations of the users, we checked and fixed the samples that are used for this task on the FSD Platform. Giving a certain vote to some samples (usually 6 over 60) gives an idea of the overall annotation process of the user, and this can help to filter very incorrect annotations. Furthermore, the examples representative for each category were checked and corrected if needed, mainly to show the semantical intra-categorial variability to the user.

3.1.2 Structure and Categories

Initially, the dataset extracted directly from the platform was like in Figure 6, where it is shown the number of trustable samples present in each category. Is it clear that some categories seem to have very few verified samples. For this reason, a choice to take only the categories with more than 90 trustable samples was made. The categories, as already mentioned, are a subset of the Audio Set ontology.

Initial 27 categories:

- Bathtub (filling or washing)
- Blender
- Chopping (food)
- Coin (dropping)

Figure 6: Initial dataset (trustable)

- Cupboard open or close
- Cutlery, silverware
- Dishes, pots, and pans
- Door
- Drawer open or close
- Electric shaver, electric razor
- Frying (food)
- Hairdryer
- Kettle Whistle
- Keys jangling
- Microwave oven
- Packing tape, duct tape
- Scissors
- Shuffling cards
- Sink (filling or washing)
- Toilet Flush

- Toothbrush
- Typing
- Vacuum cleaner
- Velcro, hook and loop fastener
- Water tap, faucet
- Writing
- Zipper (clothing)

After the filtering, the dataset looks like this (Figure 7), with 13 categories:

Figure 7: Filtered dataset

- Coin (dropping)
- Cupboard open or close
- Door
- Drawer open or close
- Keys jangling
- Microwave oven
- Packing tape, duct tape
- Scissors

- Toilet Flush
- Typing
- Vacuum cleaner
- Writing
- Zipper (clothing)

Unfortunately, we have to make a filtering operation that has no semantical significance. We have to cut categories with a less-than-a-threshold number of samples in order to give significance to our analysis. Looking at the distribution, the threshold chosen was 90 samples minimum for each category. One experiment that could be done in the future is to merge some categories that are semantically related (Chapter 3.1.3) so that they could reach the minimum number of samples required. We will see who some of these categories are in the next chapters.

Duration of samples

The duration of samples, together with the number of samples-per-category, is one of those things that can differentiate a balanced dataset and an unbalanced one. In DomesticFSD2018 the samples are taken directly from Freesound, without any modification that is not resampling and conversion to *.wav* format. This means that they have different durations, and the distributions are shown in Figure 8. In general, the dataset would be an unbalanced dataset. But, in our case, the use of frame-level aggregated features makes the duration of samples not critical for the task. By the way, it would be something to handle when dealing with models that are sensitive directly to the temporal characteristics of the samples (ex. input the spectrogram into a CNN with a patch-based approach).

Figure 8: Distributions of durations

3.1.3 Acoustic and Semantic characterization

We have already mentioned the importance of the acoustical characteristics of the samples to be able to train a model that is capable of recognizing sounds in everyday life. One important factor was to make sure that in each category there is enough variability of samples to be able to recognize sounds in different acoustic environments. This is done usually having multiple sound instances from the same source (ex. the same door opened and closed with different speed), recorded in different acoustic conditions, and also having samples from multiple sound sources that belong to the same category (ex. different kinds of doors). Luckily, being Freesound a community-based platform, users usually upload more than one sample of the same object at a time, showing the different behaviors, and they can be completely different and recorded in entirely different acoustic conditions compared the ones of other users. This also happens because users use different recording gear to record sounds.

Acoustic variability

Going deeper into acoustic variability, is also true that the variability of natural sound sources is much greater than non-natural sources. An example could be the sound of an alarm and someone yelling. In our dataset, even if the sources are

Figure 9: x axis = time, y axis = frequency(Hz). Spectrograms of two "Vacuum cleaner" samples. Is observable the different bandwidth, fundamental frequency(the "red" line is in two different y points) and temporal pattern.

often artificial, they are used in different ways and with different mechanical interactions with other objects or humans, making them behave, acoustically speaking, as they were unpredictable like natural sound sources. For example in the category "Vacuum cleaner", we have a quite characteristic sound and we would expect to have a very low variability among the samples of this category, but, as we can see from Figure 9, two randomly chosen samples can show two different characteristics both in the frequency bandwidth, fundamental frequency (various models of vacuum cleaner, different acoustic conditions during the recording, the cleaning of different materials,etc.) and temporal patterns (switching on/off,...).

Acoustic overlap

During the annotation process, we went through different issues and questionings regarding the ontology and its structure. The first problem was the acoustical overlap, often not in their entirety, of some categories. In this case, we are not

arguing the structure of the ontology, but we are pointing out the most common cases in which we thought that the user could need good examples and FAQs during the annotation process. That's why we gave the possibility, through a link to Freesound, to check the metadata that the user that uploaded the sample gave to it. Again, this should be just an help, and the final choice should be a careful evaluation of the annotator. To give an example, it was challenging to say if the source of a draining sound was coming from a bathtub drain pipe or a sink one. We found different cases like this one, and they are the following:

The draining sound of:

- Bathtub (filling or washing)
- Sink (filling or washing)

The opening and the closing sound of the lids of:

- Cupboard open or close
- Drawer open or close
- Door
- Microwave oven

The wideband sound of these household appliances:

- Hair dryer
- Vacuum cleaner
- Blender

The repetitive sound of tapping, chopping and cutting something not too hard:

- Chopping (food)
- Scissors
- Typing (only on smartphone)

The very fast spiked sounds of:

- Velcro, hook, loop fastener

- Packing tape, duct tape

Some other acoustic similarities are pointed out also in Figure 10, where we can see the distributions of zero-crossing rate, that it's commonly used to represent the noisiness of a sound. We can see that the categories "Coin (dropping)" and "Keys jangling" have very similar values, even if it was not a problem for us to distinguish them during the annotation process.

Figure 10: Distributions of Zero-crossing rate

Semantic overlap

For what concerns the semantic overlap, some categories were quite questionable and difficult to evaluate. A semantical overlap is verified when two, or more, categories are not entirely separable for their nature. These categories that follow, that appear separated in the Audio Set ontology, are quite semantically overlapping. We are talking about:

- Water Tap, faucet
- Sink (filling or washing)

During the annotation process, it was complicated for me to distinguish those categories because they share the source. One thing that is very important on the Freesound Datasets Platform is the description of the categories. This description is

taken usually from *Wikipedia* (otherwise *Wordnet*), and its role is to define the nature of each category. This is what we can read from the "Sink (filling or washing)" page:

"Sinks have taps (faucets) that supply hot and cold water and may include a spray feature to be used for faster rinsing."

This description is saying that these categories are not really on the same level of the hierarchy like they are in Audio Set, but "Water Tap, faucet" should be the child of "Sink (filling or washing)". The same thing could be said about "Bathtub (filling or washing)" because it also has a tap/faucet. This is what we can read from the *Wikipedia* page:

"Modern bathtubs have overflow and waste drains and may have taps mounted on them."

Changing the structure of the ontology could lead to a better clarification in the annotation process, but this process must be carefully done with clear criteria, as in some cases choices are highly subjective.

Furthermore, in the list of the categories, there is "Bathtub (filling or washing)" but there is no "Shower", and in the FSD mapping there are a lot of shower samples that fell under the category "Bathtub (filling or washing)". For this reason, "Shower" sounds were accepted in the "Bathtub (filling or washing)" category. We chose not to place it on the same hierarchical level because otherwise, we would have lost all the annotations done until that moment. In the future, a wise choice would be to put them on the same level in the hierarchy.

There is another category that I found missing from the ontology and could be added:

- Oven

While annotating "Microwave oven", I thought that some samples would have been more suitable for a parent category. In contrast than before, I rejected the samples

of "Oven", because they should be in a higher category than "Microwave oven" and they do not belong to the child category.

In general, even if there are some acoustic similarities and semantic overlapping between the categories, they are few compared to all the dataset and its structure (Table 2).

3.1.4 Multi-label analysis

For a sample, being an in-domain multi-label sample, in our context, means being ground truth in two or more categories of the dataset. An *in-domain* multi-label analysis was done to define the task of the project. *In-domain* means that the investigation has been done strictly among the category of DomesticFSD2018 and not outside. The result of the analysis showed that only 29 sounds out of all the dataset were present in three categories, and these categories were:

- Cupboard open or close
- Drawer open or close
- Door

for most of the samples and:

- Coin (dropping)
- Keys jangling

for only one.

This happened for two reasons. First, the metadata on Freesound was referring to two or more of these categories, so, during the mapping, the sample was mapped into two or more category waiting for the annotation. Second, during the annotation, being the samples acoustically overlapped(see Figure 2), the people could not identify the precise source of the sound, so it ended up to be classified as trustable in some or all of those categories. For this reason, I make sure, before the split of the dataset into training and testing set, to take out these 29 samples and add them later in the training set, and not in the test. In this way we can define our problem

in a *multi-class* task, and not a *multi-label* one. The difference between the two is that in the first case, in the test set the samples have only one label, and these labels are semantically non-overlapping, in the second, one sample can have one or more labels attached to it referring to different characteristics of the sound, and a different kind of approach should be used.

3.1.5 Non-trustable data

In Chapter 3.1.1 the way trustable data and non-trustable data are separated was explained. The rules followed look like this:

- *trustable* = PP_group
- *non-trustable* = PNP_group + U_group + candidates(samples with no response types/unvoted)

Figure 11: Quality estimation

For our categories, in general, the samples in *PNP_group* and *U_* voting categories are very few compared to the ones in *candidates*. In Figure 12 the amount of non-trustable data per-category is shown.

Figure 12: Non-trustable in all categories and the ones in DomesticFSD2018

Having a minimal number of trustable samples, and considering the availability of copious amounts of non-trustable data, a Semi-Supervised Learning approach is discussed. Our scenario is a typical case where a small portion of reliable annotations is available after human validation, along with a significant amount of noisy, potentially unreliable to some extent, audio data. In this context, the application of SSL fits naturally. Especially after looking at the quality estimation of the categories of DomesticFSD2018 that show it to be over 50% in all of them (Figure 11). This is the formula of how the quality estimation for each category is calculated, supposed to be a good estimation of the quality of the mapping from Freesound to Audio Set:

$$qe = (|PP_group| + |PNP_group|) / (|PP_group| + |PNP_group| + |NP_group| + |U_group|)$$

Finding a way to use the non-trustable would increase the size of the dataset from around 1700 samples to almost four times more. Considering non-trustable samples in categories with a quality estimation of less than 50% could result in adding lots of bad-mapped samples to the dataset, making it non-reliable. The central question is: is there a way to intelligently use part of this data? Some of the experiments of this project attempt to answer this research question. The goal is to machine-label some of them (the ones predicted with the highest confidence) in order to re-use it

for training recognition systems.

3.2 Models

In order to tackle the semi-supervised approach, we chose to use simple systems, built on Support Vector Machines. The input vector is a *numpy* array made by *24 values*, where the first 12 are the means between each frame of the 12 MFCCs, starting from the second, and the other 12 are the derivatives of them. In Freesound they are already calculated, so I extracted them using the Freesound APIs under the name of *lowlevel.mfcc.mean* and *lowlevel.mfcc.dmean*. The choice of using the derivatives was made to exploit characteristics of the temporal patterns of the samples. The kernel used is a *Radial Basis Function* kernel (RBF). The tuning of the parameters *C* and *gamma* is done each time using *GridSearchCV* function from *scikit-learn* [25]. The evaluation metric used is *classification accuracy* because our task is multi-class classification (to one sample corresponds one category/label), so we want to measure and evaluate the accuracy of the model of recognizing the right.

3.2.1 Supervised Learning

A SVM + MFCCs on trustable data

In the first case, the system is tested only on the trustable portion of DomesticFSD2018, so exploiting the most confident part for training the system. As we have previously said, the samples-for-category are very limited, and this is not an optimal condition for training a system.

B SVM + MFCCs on trustable data + 300 non-trustable samples

Here we want to see how the system performs adding a portion of non-trustable data keeping the dataset balanced. As we can see from the Figure 12 if we add all of them we would have a very unbalanced dataset with categories with more than a thousand samples despite others with a couple of hundreds.

C SVM + MFCCs on trustable data + all non-trustable samples

Just for analysis purposes, we try to add all the non-trustable keeping in mind the fact that we are unbalancing the dataset.

3.2.2 Semi-Supervised Learning

The idea here is to exploit one of the supervised models to make predictions on the non-trustable samples. The prediction is a result of the scikit-learn [25] function `predict_proba` and can be used with a model to calculate a vector that contains the probability of a sample of belonging to each class. We have 13 categories, so each sample is represented by 13 probabilities, one for each category. These probabilities sum up to 1, so, ideally, the maximum value should represent the most suitable category for the considered sample. In fact, from this vector, we take only the maximum, and we assign the sample to the corresponding category. The problem is that some samples, as we will see later, are represented by a very low number (ex. 0.2) that means little confidence of belonging to that category, despite being the highest one. Here we can see the distribution of these values representing the probabilities predicted by the model A. Here we can see the distribution of these

Figure 13: Distribution of probabilities predicted by model A

values representing the probabilities predicted by the model B. The next step is to select the samples to include to our training set that we will use to train other models

Figure 14: Distribution of probabilities predicted by model B

on which we will see if we are doing better than the Supervised ones. Looking at both the (Figures 13 and 14) we can see that the samples with very high confidence are way fewer than the others. With the selection of a threshold of confidence we can select precisely the level of confidence, and consequently the reliability, of the samples that we will include in the train set. For this reason, we want to compare the two selection choices:

- More data, less confidence (threshold of 0.3)
- Less data, more confidence (threshold of 0.6)

These two approaches will be applied to both our SSL models that are:

- SVM trained with trustable data + predictions from model A. **NB:** *Referred as model D1 and D2 (threshold = 0.3, 0.6 respectively)*
- SVM trained with trustable data + predictions from model B. **NB:** *Referred as model E1 and E2 (threshold = 0.3, 0.6 respectively)*

NB: *In the second case we remove the samples that from the non-trustable data are used for the first training in order not to predict on the same samples used in the training phase.*

Category	acoustically o.w.	semantically o.w.
Bathtub (filling or washing)	Sink (filling or washing)	
Blender	Vacuum Cleaner, Hair dryer	
Chopping (food)	Scissors, Typing (only on smartphone)	
Coin (dropping)		
Cupboard open or close	Door, Drawer open or close, Microwave oven(lid open/-close)	
Cutlery, silverware		
Dishes, pots, and pans		
Door	Drawer open or close, Cupboard open or close, Microwave oven(lid open/-close)	
Drawer open or close	Door, Cupboard open or close, Microwave oven(lid open/close)	
Electric shaver, electric razor		
Frying (food)		
Hair dryer	Vacuum Cleaner, Blender	
Kettle Whistle		
Keys jangling		
Microwave oven	Door, Cupboard open or close, Drawer open or close	
Packing tape, duct tape	Velcro, hook and loop fastener	
Scissors	Chopping (food), Typing (only on smartphone)	
Shuffling cards		
Sink (filling or washing)	Bathtub (filling or washing)	Water tap, faucet
Toilet flush		
Toothbrush		
Typing	Chopping (food), Scissors	
Vacuum cleaner	Hair dryer, Blender	
Velcro, hook and loop fastener	Packing tape, duct tape	
Water tap, faucet		Sink (filling or washing)
Writing		
Zipper (clothing)		

Table 2: Ambiguities (o.w. = overlapped with)

Chapter 4

Results

In this section, we will show the results of the classification accuracy achieved by the various systems. In particular, we will comment on the accuracy-per-class, and we will relate it with the quality estimation of each category in order to see its relevance. The system is always an SVM tuned with the hyperparameters (C and $gamma$) calculated at runtime by the GridSearchCV function from scikit-learn [25].

4.1 Supervised learning

4.1.1 SVM trained with trustable data - model A

Here we train the model only on the trustable part of the dataset. We can see from Table 3 that the number of samples for each category is too few for a good classification, and, in fact, the accuracy of the system is very low (43%). In this case, the quality estimation of the categories is not relevant because we are using samples that have been all manually-annotated. From Figure 15 we can see the confirmation of the bad quality of the model, observing a very noisy and unreadable confusion matrix.

Category	Accuracy	n samples train	QE
Coin (dropping)	0.56	73	0.56
Cupboard opening or closing	0.31	54	0.52
Door	0.28	89	0.65
Drawer opening or closing	0.54	74	0.72
Keys jangling	0.59	72	0.60
Microwave oven	0.36	61	0.70
Packing tape, duct tape	0.52	53	0.70
Scissors	0.43	75	0.81
Toilet flush	0.50	92	0.68
Typing	0.42	98	0.65
Vacuum cleaner	0.46	61	0.56
Writing	0.43	100	0.76
Zipper (clothing)	0.25	72	0.64
	overall	total	
	43%	974	

Table 3: Model A results

Figure 15: Confusion matrix related to the classification scores on the test set by model A

4.1.2 SVM trained with trustable data + 300 non-trustable samples - model B

Here we train the model on the trustable part of the dataset and 300 non-trustable samples randomly taken. For some categories, having 300 samples means more

than the actual available number of non-trustable samples, for others not. We can see the total number of non-trustable samples per category in figure 12. We can see from Table 4 that the number of samples for each category now is higher and the dataset remains approximatively balanced. Here the quality estimation is focal and, in fact, thanks to a good overall quality estimation for all the categories of DomesticFSD2018, we have a doubling in the overall classification accuracy (81%). We can see from figure 16 that the samples of the category "Door" are misclassified with almost every other category of the dataset, and this can be explained by its high intra-categorical variability. Keep in mind that we are working on only one level of the hierarchy, so in the "Door" category we can find, for example, samples of a door slam and, at the same time, a door squeaking.

Category	Accuracy	n samples train	QE
Coin (dropping)	0.72	373	0.56
Cupboard opening or closing	0.75	306	0.52
Door	0.40	389	0.65
Drawer opening or closing	0.95	329	0.72
Keys jangling	0.92	372	0.60
Microwave oven	0.92	342	0.70
Packing tape, duct tape	0.86	203	0.70
Scissors	0.92	275	0.81
Toilet flush	0.89	392	0.68
Typing	0.89	362	0.65
Vacuum cleaner	1	251	0.56
Writing	0.85	400	0.76
Zipper (clothing)	0.65	372	0.64
	overall	total	
	81%	4366	

Table 4: Model B results

Figure 16: Confusion matrix related to the classification scores on the test set by model B

4.1.3 SVM trained with trustable data + all non-trustable samples - model C

In this case, the model is trained with all the available data that we have. We can see from Table 5 that the number of samples per category varies a lot. In particular, we have "Coin (dropping)" and "Door" that have more than a thousand samples. This makes the dataset unbalanced, and in fact, we can see that the accuracy for those categories is way higher (around 95%) than the previous cases when the dataset was balanced. Actually, in the balanced case, the category "Door" has the lowest classification accuracy among all the categories. Furthermore, as we can see from Figure 17, quite a lot of samples are being misclassified as "Door" while they are not (11 of "Cupboard opening or closing", 11 of "Drawer opening or closing", 7 of "Microwave oven",...). This shows that, even if the overall accuracy of the model is the highest among the models (87%), the classification is not reliable.

NB: *For this reason, we will not use this system to make predictions.*

Category	Accuracy	n samples train	QE
Coin (dropping)	0.96	1230	0.56
Cupboard opening or closing	0.59	306	0.52
Door	0.93	1783	0.65
Drawer opening or closing	0.69	329	0.72
Keys jangling	0.92	395	0.60
Microwave oven	0.78	342	0.70
Packing tape, duct tape	0.71	203	0.70
Scissors	0.90	275	0.81
Toilet flush	0.98	573	0.68
Typing	0.85	362	0.65
Vacuum cleaner	0.98	251	0.56
Writing	0.89	602	0.76
Zipper (clothing)	0.9	571	0.64
	overall	total	
	87%	7222	

Table 5: Model C results

Figure 17: Confusion matrix related to the classification scores on the test set by model C

4.2 Semi-supervised learning

In this section, we use model A and model B (respectively described in Sections 4.1.1 and 4.1.2), trained with supervised techniques, in order to make predictions on the available non-trustable data. In order to select the samples we choose a threshold of

confidence, that represents the minimum value of confidence, directly proportional to the reliability of the sample, and we take all the samples with a level of confidence equal or higher than the threshold. The *confidence* is the probability of a sample of belonging to one of the categories of DomesticFSD2018. The higher it is, the more we are confident about the nature of the sample and from which category it belongs. We decided to take two cases (more samples with less confidence, fewer samples with more confidence). The choice of the thresholds 0.3 and 0.6 was made referring to figure 13 and 14 and trying higher and lower values. Choosing a threshold of 0.2 included to the dataset a lot of samples from "Coin(dropping)" and "Door", making the dataset unbalanced (these categories have way more non-trustable samples than the others). On the other hand, choosing a threshold higher than 0.6 resulted in a selection too strict and in a non-relevant change in the dataset. Looking at the distributions of probabilities this consideration is made in both the two semi-supervised models. In the tables of the results, we will show the number of samples used in the training phase of each model. This number represents the sum of the trustable samples in the training set plus the samples predicted by the corresponding supervised model.

4.2.1 SVM trained with trustable data + predictions from model A (models D1 and D2)

In this case, the model used to make predictions is model A. It is the one trained with few samples and, for this, with very low accuracy.

threshold = 0.3 - model D1

Here we can see that the overall accuracy on the test set is also lower (41%) than the one obtained by the model who makes the predictions (model A), and this is because we are taking a high number of samples but a lot of them have a very low confidence, as we can see from figure 13. The accuracy is so low that the confusion matrix is too noisy and with many misclassifications, as we can see in Figure 18. The results of the classification on the test set are shown in Table 6.

Category	Accuracy	n samples train	QE
Coin (dropping)	0.61	460	0.56
Cupboard opening or closing	0.28	107	0.52
Door	0.21	376	0.65
Drawer opening or closing	0.51	439	0.72
Keys jangling	0.59	316	0.60
Microwave oven	0.36	239	0.70
Packing tape, duct tape	0.26	105	0.70
Scissors	0.41	302	0.81
Toilet flush	0.55	439	0.68
Typing	0.45	331	0.65
Vacuum cleaner	0.46	230	0.56
Writing	0.43	415	0.76
Zipper (clothing)	0.17	208	0.64
	overall	total	
	44%	1326	

Table 6: Model D1 results

threshold = 0.6 - model D2

Here we take fewer non-trustable samples but with higher confidence and, in fact, the overall accuracy is slightly better, but still low (44%). Also here, the accuracy is so low that the confusion matrix is too noisy and with many misclassifications, as we can see, again, in Figure 18. The results of the classification on the test set are shown in Table 7.

Category	Accuracy	n samples train	QE
Coin (dropping)	0.59	207	0.56
Cupboard opening or closing	0.28	54	0.52
Door	0.28	89	0.65
Drawer opening or closing	0.54	97	0.72
Keys jangling	0.59	111	0.60
Microwave oven	0.36	61	0.70
Packing tape, duct tape	0.52	53	0.70
Scissors	0.43	75	0.81
Toilet flush	0.52	149	0.68
Typing	0.42	101	0.65
Vacuum cleaner	0.47	145	0.56
Writing	0.43	112	0.76
Zipper (clothing)	0.27	72	0.64
	overall	total	
	41%	3967	

Table 7: Model D2 results

Figure 18: Confusion matrices related to the classification scores on the test set by D1 and D2

4.2.2 SVM trained with trustable data + predictions from model B - models E1 and E2

In this other case, the model used to make predictions is model B. Model B is the one with the most promising characteristics (See Section 4.1.2), with a good overall

accuracy and a "rich" approximately balanced train set. In fact, the number of samples per category is not big but neither small (Table 3) as in model A (See Section 4.1.1).

The results are very similar with both thresholds (Tables 8, 9), and still very similar to model B (Table 4). The overall accuracy of both systems is 81%. This is because the non-trustable data added in both models E1 and E2 in the training phase does not provide more information to the classification task than the one added in the model B from the model A. This shows that the predictions are coherent with the quality estimation of the categories coming from FSD, because, first, thanks to that, we increase the quality of the model going from model A to model B, so using samples labeled following the original mapping (the one that the quality estimation refers to). Then, we keep the same accuracy of 81% also in the models E1 and E2, where part of the training set is predicted and consequently machine-labeled (not doing worse, but not even improving it).

Furthermore, the difference of samples between the two models is not enough to make noticeable improvements in the classification accuracy (See Tables 4, 8, 9). Having them the same accuracy we will take the model that uses more samples for the training, in order to consider them a trustable part of the dataset. In fact, having a lower threshold has the advantage to allow us to include more samples in our dataset (Table 8), and that's what we want to do. We can see also a couple of interesting things here. The category "Scissors" jumped from 43%(Table 3) of accuracy to 92%. This can explain and confirm that our quality estimation of 81% is correct. The same kind of jump is done by the "Vacuum cleaner" category, going from 46% to 100%. We saw in Figure 8 in Section 3.1.2 that it's the category with the longest samples. Even if we are using aggregated features, we could say that it's still an influencing factor, in addition to quite different acoustic characteristics compared to the other categories in DomesticFSD2018. Some misclassification is also due to the acoustic overlapping mentioned before. We can see in Figure 19 that some samples of "Door" are misclassified in both cases with "Cupboard open and closing" and "Drawer open and closing". The same thing happens with "Coin

(dropping)" and "Keys jangling".

Furthermore, we can see that in all the models the category "Door" has the lowest accuracy, and that's probably because it's the category with the widest intra-categorical variability and where we are considering in one parent category ℓ children in order to have only one level of the hierarchy.

Category	Accuracy	n samples train	QE
Coin (dropping)	0.72	709	0.56
Cupboard opening or closing	0.75	362	0.52
Door	0.42	698	0.65
Drawer opening or closing	0.87	426	0.72
Keys jangling	0.90	455	0.60
Microwave oven	0.89	443	0.70
Packing tape, duct tape	0.86	226	0.70
Scissors	0.92	314	0.81
Toilet flush	0.92	543	0.68
Typing	0.89	397	0.65
Vacuum cleaner	1	268	0.56
Writing	0.80	564	0.76
Zipper (clothing)	0.67	486	0.64
	overall	total	
	81%	5891	

Table 8: Model E1 results

Figure 19: Confusion matrices related to the classification scores on the test set by E1 and E2

Category	Accuracy	n samples train	QE
Coin (dropping)	0.72	452	0.56
Cupboard opening or closing	0.75	308	0.52
Door	0.40	401	0.65
Drawer opening or closing	0.95	340	0.72
Keys jangling	0.92	381	0.60
Microwave oven	0.92	346	0.70
Packing tape, duct tape	0.86	205	0.70
Scissors	0.92	280	0.81
Toilet flush	0.89	433	0.68
Typing	0.89	364	0.65
Vacuum cleaner	0.98	253	0.56
Writing	0.85	427	0.76
Zipper (clothing)	0.65	379	0.64
	overall	total	
	81%	4569	

Table 9: Model E2 results

Here we have an overview of the results (Table 10):

Model	Balanced/Unbalanced	Accuracy	total dataset size (n samples)
A	balanced	43%	1606
B	balanced	81%	4998
C	unbalanced	87%	7854(max)
D1	balanced	41%	4599
D2	balanced	44%	1958
E1	balanced	81%	6523
E2	balanced	81%	5201

Table 10: Overview

Finally, we can see from Table 10 that the model E1 is the model with the best characteristics in order to obtain a balanced dataset with the best classification accuracy. Using this model, the dataset size increase from 1606 samples(trustable set) to 5891 for the training plus 632 of the test set = 6523 (6532 - 974 = 5558 non-trustable samples added).

Chapter 5

Conclusions and Future work

The first goal of this project was the creation of a new dataset of domestic sound events in an attempt to overcome the lack of annotated data we have for domestic event recognition applications. As part of the Freesound Datasets project, we have been able to annotate and help the community annotating in the most transparent and less biased way, obtaining a very relevant dataset for the research community that will be published soon. However, and although DomesticFSD2018 is a significant contribution, we would still need more data for a complete analysis, mainly because current machine learning trends require way more data than this. Also, we had to exclude almost half of the categories from the original domestic subset of Audio Set because the number of trustable samples was not enough to make significant considerations, and this is a limitation for a real application of the system. An accurate analysis both acoustical and semantical has been done to facilitate the comprehension of the ontology and the future work that could be done to improve it was suggested. Another improvement that should be done in the future is a multi-label annotation of the samples, tackling also the polyphonic nature of overlapping sounds. This dataset is the first step of work that still needs to be done in this field.

Our second goal was to research on the efficiency of both supervised and semi-supervised approach on our data to see the actual value of the non-trustable part of the dataset, and if it could be used somehow to improve sound recognition systems

and increase the size of the trustable portion. The main reasons were two:

- optimize resources in the annotation process that are needed for human annotators
- the availability (and potential exploitation) of a large amount of audio samples that have received no human validation (hence belong to the non-trustable portion)

The first system proposed, using Supervised techniques, shows that only the trustable part of the dataset is not enough to achieve satisfactory recognition rates, while adding a number of candidates (following the original mapping and without a proper selection, hence potentially mislabelled) doubles the accuracy.

The second part of the experiments using Semi-Supervised techniques, allow us to first, confirm that the quality estimation of FSD is reliable, and second, that exploiting a system trained with trustable-data plus some non-trustable can lead us to make more accurate predictions and increase the size of the trustable part of the dataset.

In particular, we found that one of the semi-supervised models (E1, See Chapter 4.2.2) was the best model in terms of accuracy (81%) and number of samples used in the training phase. The samples used in the training phase are mostly non-trustable, but they are considered as trustable during the training of the model. The semi-supervised learning approach allows us to consider samples that before were not considered trustworthy as they were manually annotated.

Furthermore, we could say that adding non-trustable samples in categories with an high QE results almost always in an increase in accuracy (especially from the first to the second Supervised models (model A and B) that have the most significant increase in the number of training samples), and this is because more good samples add more acoustic variability to the data in each category. Thanks to this, the model is able to generalize better.

Now that more data is available for research purposes, an experiment with more complex techniques could be done. Deep learning techniques, like Neural Networks, can be trained on this dataset for the task of classification. In particular, Convolutional Neural Networks have been widely used lately for this task [12]. These networks come from the image recognition world, so they are very efficient when inputting 2D shaped data. For this reason, the time-frequency representation (*spectrogram*) of audio samples is usually used as input to these networks. One major issue to be handled is, however, the duration of the samples. For being inputted to a CNN, the audio samples (so the spectrograms) should have all the same duration/length. Regarding this issue two possibilities can be evaluated:

- make some selections and/or modifications on the available samples considering their duration (cropping, selecting only the ones with the same length, etc.)
- use a patch-based approach when inputting the spectrogram to the network (inputting the spectrograms as a sum of smaller frames all of the same size)

The first approach is invasive on the data and should be done very carefully. The second is a technique that affects the model but preserves the data.

Chapter 6

Reproducibility

The code of this project is available on *GitHub* with the description of each file. In the repository, you will find the code to build, split, and characterize the dataset, and train and validate the presented models.

<https://github.com/anielrossi/DomesticEventRecognitionSSL>

The DomesticEvent2018 dataset has not been published yet, but it will be released as part of the Freesound Datasets Platform soon.

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